

HIGH TEMPERATURE COMPATIBILITY OF CARBON FIBER WITH ITS COPPER AND NICKEL COATINGS

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ABSTRACT

In this experiment, a kind of high strength PAN-based carbon fiber was heat-treated at a range of 400-950°C for two hours in flowing hydrogen of 99.5% purity after having been uniformly coated with copper and nickel layers by electroless deposition respectively, and then the room-temperature fracture strength of the fibers was measured. The change of coating morphology was observed by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Meanwhile, the effect of coating elements on the structure of the fibers at elevated temperature was assessed by electron probe micro-analyser, X-ray diffraction analysis and SEM observation. Particular care was taken for nickel-coated fibers. In the end, the degrading mechanism of fibers by coatings after high temperature treatment was briefly discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber surface coatings must be applied by various methods such as electroless deposition, electroplating, vapour deposition and plasma spraying et al for the sake of modifying the fiber surface characteristics, enhancing the fiber-matrix wettability and adhesion, and preventing deterioration in fiber properties at elevated temperature. In the meantime, however, the high temperature compatibility of carbon fiber with its coating arises during the fabrication and high temperature service of composites. It is simply because that most metal matrix composites can be regarded as non-equilibrium systems and hence a gradient of chemical potential exists at the fiber-coating and coating-matrix interfaces. This difference in chemical potential provides the driving force for diffusion or chemical interaction when the composites are heated at high temperature [1].

It is well known that copper and nickel are two kinds of widely used surface coatings of carbon fibers or matrix materials for metal matrix

composites. The influence of nickel or copper coating on the room-temperature fracture strength and microstructure of carbon fiber after heat treatment in vacuum has been investigated by many researchers [2, 4 - 6], but the work in which hydrogen is used as atmosphere gas is scarcely reported. Because at high temperature hydrogen can reduce the oxides of copper, cobalt and nickel et al, it is worth considering to employ hydrogen atmosphere when just-mentioned metals are served as matrix metals of composites and incorporated with carbon fiber by solid diffusion method. For example, by powder-slurry infiltration followed by hot pressing in hydrogen, we have successfully fabricated carbon fiber reinforced copper matrix composite.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIAL AND TECHNIQUE

In this work, PAN-based high strength carbon fiber yarns were used. The fiber yarn consists of 3,000 monofilaments which have a diameter of approximate 6 μm with a average strength of about 3,000 MN/m^2 . After having been uniformly coated with 0.7-1.0 μm layers of nickel containing 20.05 at.% phosphorus and copper by electroless deposition method respectively, the carbon fibers were held at different temperature for 2 hr in a flowing hydrogen of 99.5% purity and subsequently the room temperature tensile strength was measured in an Instron tensile test machine using a 3mm gage length and a tensile speed of 5mm/min.

The specimens of carbon fiber/resin were made for the structure observation. When performing an experiment on electron probe micro-analyser, it must be stressed that fibers with coatings should be strictly normal to the cross section of specimen.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The effect of heat treatment on the surface morphology of coating

SEM observation shew that after treatment at about 750°C, nickel coating began to spheroidize and had broken up into a series of spheroidal particles at 900°C, partially departing from fibers. But for thicker nickel coating, it was also possible that nickel coating started to aggregate and coarse to form a net coating by means of the migration and merge of crystal boundary at 850°C, showing no obvious spheroidization, as shown in Fig. 1a.

a. Ni-coated fibers
after 800°C/2hr
treatment.

b. Cu-coated fibers
after 650°C/2hr
treatment.

c. Cu-coated fibers
after 750°C/2hr
treatment.

Figure 1. The morphology of coatings after heat treatment in different condition by SEM.

The threshold temperature for copper coating to spheroidize depended on the thickness of the coating and the rate of heating-colding cycle. For thin copper coating (e.g., 0.5 μ m) and the more rapid rate (e.g., 30°C/min), the spheroidization occurred at a lower temperature of 500°C and had come to be distinct at 650°C (Fig. 1b). When reaching 900°C, a large number of copper spheres had detached from the fibers and only the minority of them attached the surface ditches and microcracks of carbon fibers, referring to Fig. 3. From Fig. 3 it is also shown that only point contact existed between the fiber and coating and therefore the surface wetting was poor. Contrarily, in the case of thicker copper coating (e.g., 1.5 μ m) and slower speed of heating or colding (e.g., 5°C/min), spheroidization did not take place until a temperature as high as 750°C, as Fig. 1c shows.

Spheroidization is a process of surface diffusion accompanied by a reduction of surface energy and therefore thin coating will be easy to spheroidize. Besides, the mismatch in the coefficient of thermal expansion of both the components will give rise to thermal stresses of considerable magnitude in the condition of varying temperature, which will weaken the bond between coating and fiber or even results in the breakup of coating. The higher temperature and slighter tendency of spheroidization of nickel coating is mainly contributed to its stronger adhesion force to carbon fibers than copper coating.

The changing of fracture strength of carbon fibers after heat treatment

The changing of room temperature fracture strength of the carbon fibers with respect to heat treatment temperature is plotted in Fig. 2. At first sight, there was considerable scatter in the mechanical property, which was caused by several reasons [2, 3]. The first is the macroscopic defects such as precipitation and pit on fiber surface, gas pocket and crack inside fibers. The second reason is the microscopic difference in carbonating temperature, microcrystalline configuration and its orientation degree of fibers et. al.. The third may come from the surface damage introduced during fiber handling.

Figure 2. The room temperature fracture strength of carbon fibers after heat treatment at different temperature for 2hr in flowing hydrogen (each datum point is the average value of five specimens).

From Fig. 2, it was shown that the average fracture strength of uncoated and copper-coated fibers was almost unaffected (i.e., the average value was within the standard deviation) by treatment of 2hr up to 750°C. After holding over 750°C, with a increase in temperature, the fracture strength of fibers decreased appreciably, with a greater reduction in strength of copper-coated fibers than uncoated fiber. At 950°C, the copper-coated fibers were weakened by some 50%. However, even after treatment at temperature as low as 600°C, the strength of nickel-coated fibers started to reduce drastically and had been completely lost when up to 900°C, indicating the crumpling of fiber

structure, which is generally in agreement with the result of R. Warren et al. [4].

The structure change of treated carbon fibers

Heat-treated fibers with copper or nickel coating were examined by an electron probe microanalyser so as to determine the concentration distribution of coating elements within fibers. Typical line trace of Cu and Ni along the diameter of the fibers was shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

Figure 3. Intensity of Cu in the Cu-coated carbon fiber by electron probe microanalyser after heat treatment at 900°C for 2hr in a flowing hydrogen.

Figure 4. Intensity of nickel in the Ni-coated fibers by probe electron analyser after heat treatment at 850°C for 2hr in an flowing hydrogen.

From Fig. 3, one can see that after 900°C/2hr treatment, copper from the coating did not enter into fibers. In contrast to this, the nickel element from the coating partially migrated into carbon fiber in the form of such a super-dispersoid as not to be identified by SEM observation (Fig. 4) and hence it is different from the results obtained by many workers where the nickel migrated towards the center of carbon fibers as ring or bulk of nickel after exposure to high temperature in vacuum [4-7].

X-ray diffraction analysis was carried out to examine the structural change of nickel-coated fibers by holding at elevated temperature, as shown in Fig. 5. The (002) diffraction peak of non-treated nickel-coated fibers was more smooth and broad, while with increasing temperature and approaching 600°C, the peak became somewhat higher and sharper, indicating that a certain amount of recrystallization had occurred in nickel-coated fibers. From the X-ray diffraction analysis, it was also found that after treatment above 400°C, a new Ni₃P phase appeared. No any compound of nickel with

carbon existed in the diffraction profile.

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction profiles of carbon (002) on Ni-coated fibers after holding at different temperature for 2 hr in flowing hydrogen.

Discussion about the strength degradation of treated fibers

Considering above experimental analyses, it seems reasonable to think that the reduction in strength of uncoated and copper-coated fibers at temperature $>750^{\circ}\text{C}$ mainly results from an oxygen concentration in the furnace atmosphere which is sufficient for reaction with the carbon to form carbon-monoxide [4, 6, 7]. The larger strength reduction of Cu-coated fibers after the equivalent treatment is presumably due to the catalyzing of copper coating to the reaction, particularly in the case of the active copper reduced by hydrogen.

In present paper, the reason why the nickel-coated carbon fibers were severely weakened by treatment at temperature $>600^{\circ}\text{C}$ in hydrogen probably lies in the fact that at elevated temperature nickel coating catalyzes the reaction of hydrogen with carbon to form hydrocarbon [4], which is again promoted by the recrystallization of fibers activated by the migration of nickel into carbon fibers. In addition, the slight recrystallization of carbon fibers and the surface attack come from oxygen in furnace atmosphere at high temperature seems to be responsible for the heavy degradation in strength. These kinds of gas reactions can be confirmed by the decrease in

the cross section area of fibers after high temperature treatment.

The precise nature of the recrystallization process of nickel-coated fiber or the migration of nickel into carbon fiber has not been established with certainty. Jackson et al suggested that it occurred by the dissolution in nickel of carbon from fibers followed by its reprecipitation as crystalline graphite, while Warren and Wood have argued that alternative process is activated by nickel atoms, but not involving dissolution in nickel, which seems to be consistent with our result. The reactions of hydrogen and oxygen with carbon destroys the establishment of C-Ni bond so that the nickel can not migrate into carbon fiber by the dissolution-diffusion-reprecipitation process. However, it is possible that the entrance of a little amount of nickel into carbon fibers is by way of narrow spacing between crystallites, microcrack and other various intrinsic defects within carbon fibers. After all, more detailed study remains to be done so as to well explain these phenomena.

CONCLUSION

1. After heat treatment above 750°C, an electronless deposition nickel coating begin to spheroidize and have broken up into a series of spheroidal particles when reaching 900°C.
2. The threshold temperature for the copper coating to spheroidize is uncertain and to a great extent depends on the thickness of copper coating and the rate of heating-colding cycle.
3. The room-temperature average fracture strength of uncoated and copper-coated fibers is almost unaffected by treatment up to 750°C for 2 hr in a flowing hydrogen. After treatment above 750°C, with an increase in temperature, their strength decreases appreciably, with a greater reduction in strength for copper-coated fibers than uncoated's. At temperature >600°C, the strength of nickel-coated fibers starts to reduce drastically and have been completely lost when up to 900°C.
4. A small amount of nickel element from coating migrates into carbon fiber in the form of super-dispersoid and slight recrystallization occurs in nickel-coated fibers after high temperature treatment.

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